

**COMPETENCY IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE
IN GENERAL MARIANO ALVAREZ, CAVITE IN THE
NEW NORMAL**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 7

Pages: 803-812

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2100

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12879479

Manuscript Accepted: 07-01-2024

Competency in Teaching English as a Second Language in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite in the New Normal

Robert Niño O. Ponce,* Rochelle P. Cañares
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted human life, affecting public health, food systems, and the educational sector. This study investigates the competence of English teachers in private and public schools in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite, within the context of the new normal brought about by the pandemic. Using a descriptive research method, the study surveyed 330 respondents. The findings indicate that issues related to online and hybrid learning were minimal, though there was moderate concern about institutional support and training opportunities for teachers. Teachers demonstrated high competence in classroom management, particularly in maintaining discipline. Their qualifications and experience met the standards set by the Department of Education (DepEd) and civil service, ensuring their proficiency in delivering content. Teachers effectively connected current lessons to previous topics and real-life situations, highlighting their mastery of the subject matter. Moreover, the study revealed that teachers excelled in using diverse teaching techniques, boosting students' self-esteem, and recognizing their achievements. They were also proficient in conducting technical feasibility studies and action research to enhance teaching efficiency and effectiveness, particularly in technological courses. Teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings confirmed their very satisfactory performance. The research concludes that teachers' instructional competence and performance are significant and unique. Recommendations include more frequent training and seminars for teachers, improved evaluation and monitoring systems by school heads, and programs to help teachers balance work and career during the pandemic. Further studies should explore school administrators' leadership skills and their impact on school performance and operations.

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, competency in teaching English, second language*

Introduction

Human life has been devastated by the COVID-19 outbreak, which poses a major threat to public health, food systems, as well as the world of the teaching profession. The pandemic has had a terrible effect on the economy and society, with millions of businesses facing an existential threat from the shutdown of businesses and institutions (Chriscaden, 2020). Because of lockdowns and community quarantines, most educational institutions around the world have been forced to close temporarily, leading to a shift away from traditional learning toward virtual or online learning. Schools consider the current situation in developing and implementing the "new normal educational policy" wherein the circumstance presents a unique challenge to the decision-making approach of educational leaders. As a result, teachers must practice instructional competency in classroom management, faculty qualification and experience, mastery of the subject taught, strategies and techniques in teaching and research, and extension projects to maintain the delivery of high-quality education in every school (Tria, 2020).

Competence involves the ability to deal with all types of challenges in both the profession and in daily life. Sieck (2020) indicated that the solutions for succeeding as a leader in an organization encompass a wider variety of skill sets aside from leadership capabilities. Thus, it is vital for different teachers to have certain approaches to thinking and acting to do assigned tasks. Teachers have a major impact on the development of a community. The Philippines' long-term development and advancement depend on integrated students who are both rooted in values and skilled in 21st-century abilities (DepED Order No. 36, s. 2013).

According to Gamayao and Biñas (2021), teaching and learning are considered two parts of instruction. Teachers must have a high degree of expertise and pedagogical abilities in the subject they are teaching to be more effective and successful. The competency of a teacher includes the abilities, understanding, and mentality that enable them to fulfill their district-assigned obligations.

One of the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown is that schools around the world were closed. König et al. (2020) revealed that digital teacher competence and teacher education opportunities to develop digital competence are important in adjusting to online learning. The digital competence of teachers is highly needed since online distance learning is highly utilized. As per Barron et al. (2020), teachers' responsibilities are changing at a rapid pace, making teaching now, in many respects, more challenging than when only one-on-one teaching was used. Teachers now have to dedicate a greater amount of time to instructing, communicating with learners, and other administrative duties. The pandemic underscored those teachers and students need more flexibility.

Despite working from their respective homes, teachers and principals have been charged with the task of updating and adjusting course syllabuses and standards as they transitioned to online classes. Learning systems such as Moodle, Canvas, and Blackboard, as well as software including Google Meet, Zoom, and Video chat, have been used in classrooms in which teachers and students have access to online systems and decent Internet associations. Educators and administrators used mobile phones to send information, remarks, and equipment to schools where people had limited access to computers or undependable Internet access (Simbulan, 2020).

As society changes to embrace technological futures, the way and what teachers teach in our educational system will alter and need to be enhanced to keep up with the expanding demands of the twenty-first century. The teacher's role in using information and communication technology (ICT) in the teaching-learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic is critical (Espino-Díaz et al., 2020). Teachers must have pedagogical training in understanding the use of ICT in teaching. By doing this, new educational styles will be made easier to emerge to successfully impart new knowledge to students.

As a career path that is extremely close to learners and a field of study which is always available to help students maximize their skills, it is essential for a teacher to start optimizing productivity (Intan & Ahmad, 2016). The quality of students is a result of high-quality education. Teachers become critical success factors when it comes to providing high-quality education.

Lepp et al. (2021) implied that decisions teachers make in teaching affect their students' learning performance. Teachers' teaching-related actions are impacted by elements such as digital technologies' existence and capability to be used. To maintain class connection and to aid students' motivation, teachers made most of their teaching decisions based on aims that were more temporary in nature, such as promoting social contact.

The study by Iqbal et al. (2019) found that students' evaluation of their lecturers' competency influences the learning satisfaction and experience of learners. Therefore, excellent lectures guarantee greater learning outcomes for students. Student-teacher interaction is associated with a positive connection. Teachers who are given the freedom and support to express themselves creatively have a significant impact on not just students' learning but also the development of their character qualities.

The European Training Foundation (2020) indicated that teachers have a critical role to play in increasing students' participation in education in areas affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the most difficult problems for distance learning during the COVID-19 crisis is keeping learners interested and involved. The absence of face-to-face interactions, the difficulty of communicating through digital devices, and the necessity to arrange one's own time can all pose extra hurdles to learners' ability to assimilate new knowledge and keep track of their progress in the learning process. When it comes to ensuring that students remain engaged and do not lose their enthusiasm, the role of the teacher becomes increasingly important. As a result, having an important level of instructional competency and the ability to give a high-quality education to students is significant.

In connection, Hartini et al. (2018) concluded that the development of educational competence is a significant factor in the improvement of teacher performance. To provide students with efficient and appropriate learning, the teacher must keep on improving pedagogical and instructional competence. The development of pedagogic competence can be accomplished with a variety of competency development methods.

Education is thought of as both knowledge construction and competence, as well as the possibility for growth and improvement. Moreover, the expectation is that students will be able to learn regardless of the constraints of time and location. Another major challenge in teaching is to provide students with chances to think when they perform various tasks, such as problem-solving, analysis, and synthesizing (Sootipon, 2010).

While many poor students in developing countries are still unable to purchase devices for virtual learning, Murgatrottd (2020) mentioned that online education faces the risk of increasing the amount of time a student spends in front of a screen or computer monitor. Another perceived obstacle is a lack of family assistance, particularly for young students because both parents are employed. Virtual learning has a lot of challenges these recent times.

According to Abuhammad (2020), individual factors were the most visible barrier to online learning. The biggest challenges to realizing strategic goals are a lack of training and assistance, inadequate technical expertise, lack of knowledge, poor communication with professionals, and incompetency qualification. The frequent hurdle mentioned was a lack of training in online learning.

Furthermore, Baticulon et al. (2021) stressed that the transition to online learning was difficult for medical students in the Philippines, who encountered multiple interconnected obstacles. The two most frequently observed issues were struggling to modify learning approaches and having to fulfill commitments at home. When it comes to tackling these concerns during the COVID-19 outbreak and beyond, medical schools and educators play a critical role by offering student-centered solutions to the problem. In relation to the ongoing study, one of the responsibilities of teachers is to search out practical solutions and alternatives to the problem to provide students with high-quality knowledge. The flexible learning strategy described by Rojas II (2021) relates to the utilization of a wide variety of approaches which include online internet and mobile/typed learning materials to help students achieve their educational goals. This current strategy features a wide variety of teaching and learning approaches, which are dependent on a student's particular situation.

In line with this, most student participants revealed in the study of Muthuprasad et al. (2021) that online lessons could be much more difficult than traditional school sessions, caused by technological limitations, disrupted responses, as well as the teacher's failure to manage the process of technology. In a knowledgeable society, teachers are obligated to enforce methods that increase students' learning while also developing the skills and competencies necessary to cope with the challenges of a constantly changing and complex society. Mazariegos (2020) noted that teachers will need a new educational strategy that is more essential and innovative in terms of developing creative projects in which they will act as facilitators of learning to accomplish this. The new responsibilities of teachers necessitate us

staying abreast of developments in the field of schooling.

Gotinga (2020) asserted that while the Department of Education (DepEd) believes in teachers' "up-skilling" and "re-skilling". The government should support students' educational and training goals before attempting to upskill and re-skill instructors. This is to help the teachers reach higher competency when it comes to teaching.

According to Lapitan et al. (2021), educational technologies, such as virtual learning environments, demand that teachers change the traditional teaching methods of the past to use new approaches alongside emerging technologies. To discover the problems with online education, teachers should discuss with students in class the teaching method. It is also a good way to check if students are catching up with lectures, which enables them to identify various issues related to online learning.

Teachers who aim to excel in online learning should comprehend instructional materials and syllabus, as well as evaluation concepts (CoSN, 2020). The successful implementation of new technology depends on the cooperation of education, subject matter, and innovation organizations. When a school makes the effort to help students transition from the classroom to the workplace, they must act swiftly while also utilizing all their employees and resources. For all intents and purposes, ICT has played a crucial role in transforming the education sectors all over the world.

Additionally, expertise in teaching was of extremely high quality, particularly regarding curriculum and learning management. Prasertcharoensuk et al. (2015) discovered that teachers are extremely concerned about curriculum and knowledge management. To boost students' learning accomplishments, educational staff development must be conducted to ensure excellent instructional management of teachers.

Tongson and Eslit (2018) suggested that for teachers to improve instructional competencies, school heads must encourage teachers to learn meaningful and exciting teaching methods, motivate them to deal with global and functional patterns in education, and provide benefits or accreditation for exceptional teaching practices.

It is very important for any teacher to improve their competency in the instructions. To improve the quality of teacher instruction, the advancement of competencies recognized as 21st-century skills is receiving more attention. Nevertheless, bringing about desired improvements is difficult due to a lack of context-specific knowledge of instructional practices and effective ways to support teacher professional development (Kim et al., 2019). According to Kim, et al. (2019), the identification and evaluation of instructors' teaching abilities when it comes to the effective use of instructional materials is critical in today's educational environment.

In the present educational system, it is basic to realize how well educators can use accessible assets. Subsequently, the analyst plans to survey the educational ability of educators working in both private and state funded schools. It is necessary to evaluate their competence in order to determine whether instructional resources are appropriate for the current learning mode. The purpose of the study is to identify and assess teachers' instructional competence. A proposal for an intervention that will contribute to the process of improving the instructional competency of teachers in both public and private schools will be developed based on the study's findings and analysis.

Research Questions

The study aims to describe the competence of the teachers in teaching English subjects from both private and public schools in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite the new normal brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic. Particularly, the study answered the following:

1. What are the problems that are encountered in the online and hybrid learning?
2. What is the level of instructional competence of the English teachers in public and private schools in the COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of:
 - 2.1. classroom management;
 - 2.2. teachers/faculty qualification and experience;
 - 2.3. mastery of subject taught;
 - 2.4. methods, techniques and strategies used in teaching; and
 - 2.5. research and extension projects?
3. What is the performance of the teachers as assessed in the IPCRF rating?
4. Is there a significant difference between the instructional competence of the teachers and the performance of the teachers as assessed by both students and colleague?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized descriptive method of research which is a type of quantitative study. In this method, as stated by McCombes (2019), aims to correctly and systematically describe the situation or phenomenon. The descriptive method of research uses a wide variety of quantitative and qualitative methods to study one or more variables. Additionally, it is ideal for the study to use a descriptive research design since it aims to describe the characteristics of instructional competencies of public and private teachers without changing any of the variables in the study.

The study shall determine the instructional competency of the public and private teachers. The study will utilize quantitative data as part of its sources for analysis.

This kind of study has been used for this research since the method used in this kind of study is appropriate to the needs of the study. Using the data gathering strategy used in descriptive method, a better understanding in regards to instructional competence can be identified. Moreover, the research is found to be more reliable when it uses quantitative data gathering strategies.

Participants

The purposive sampling technique was utilized. According to Foley (2018), purposive sampling can be named also judgmental sampling. It is a non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on self-judgment. According to Alchemer (2021), the random sampling is a sampling strategy which uses Slovin's Formula to denote the number of respondents from the population. In this method, the researcher requires to have prior learning on the purpose of the study. The researcher focused on students on the Senior High School who are enrolled in one (1) Private and one (1) Public School found in General Mariano Alvarez in Cavite. The respondent schools are chosen based on the availability and accessibility of the school from the researcher's location. From this, a total of 836 students are gathered from the two schools. From the total number of populations, using Slovin's formula, the researcher has decided to utilize a total of 264 respondents which barely represents the total population of the students. The sample size is generated with a margin of error of 5%. The confidence level for this sample size is 95%. In order to achieve the number of samples, the researcher has asked individuals of about 330.

Instruments

The study utilized the self-administered survey questionnaire. In this questionnaire, the researcher aims to gain information on the main concept of the study. The questionnaire with questions formulated by the researcher aims to elicit objective answers to the questions that will be raised in the study. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part will identify the respondent of the participant that may reflect to be useful in the study. To present the distribution of respondents by means of their demographic profile. These groups would determine if there is a significance when compared to instructional competence of teachers in selected private and in public schools. The second part will determine the instructional competence of the teachers in public and private institutions. The second part is evaluated using the 5-point Likert Scale. Below is a table that clearly shows the details of the 5-point Likert Scale. The range in the scale is used in order to prevent any biases in the average responses of the researcher. From the responses, the range can identify the average point without having bias interpretation.

Table 1. 5-Point Likert Scale

Score	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Highly Competent
4	3.41 – 4.20	Competent
3	2.61 – 3.39	Moderately Competent
2	1.81 – 2.59	Less Competent
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not Competent

Procedure

The researcher gathers quantitative data. This is accomplished by gathering the perceptions of respondents targeted by the researcher in this study. The researcher has decided to do the following procedures for the data gathering of the study.

Before gathering data, the researcher must first obtain permission from the college dean and the thesis adviser to perform the study. A request letter will then be addressed to the Division of City Schools to undertake research involving data collection via a survey questionnaire at the target schools where the respondents will be taken.

Once accepted, the researcher will approach the principal of the selected school for assistance and permission to conduct a survey of the target participants.

Following the approval of the request, the distribution of the survey questionnaire must be completed immediately and distributed accordingly.

The data gathering process is then launched once all responders have completed filling out the required information and data.

The researcher analyzes data for the final procedure, which is interpreted using statistical methods as described in the following section.

Data Analysis

The gathered data will be treated with the help of the statistician using the following formulas:

Frequency Count and Percentage Formula – this will be used to present the demographic profile of respondents according to their descriptions such as age, gender, etc. These will also present the proper distribution of the respondents. This tool is very appropriate in presenting the frequency and the percentage of each response the item in the survey gets. This tool is very useful in identifying the

intensity and frequency of the responses on the survey questionnaire. The data in this tool shall present the values of the responses on each respondents.

Weighted Mean- This tool was applied to determine the composite average of the perceptions per item as assessed and evaluated by the respondents with the use of the Self-made Survey Questionnaire. This tool is a good thing to use for the study to determine the intensity of the response for each item in the survey. This tool is efficient since it provides a correct number of intensity for the data gathering. The tool has the data that evaluates the total average of the responses of the participants. This gives the researcher insight on the common response of the respondents.

T-test (Homoscedastic): This was a statistical tool utilized to determine the significant difference between two or more variables that are used in the study. Thus, this tool will be useful in differentiating the variables in this study. T-test usually used when two values are to be compared on its significant difference. As the tool presents, data in this part simply identifies whether two variables are different or related. This helps in identifying whether there are relativity or differentiable between variables.

Ethical Considerations

The participants were sent consent forms ahead of time that ask if they are voluntarily joining the study and they allowed the researchers to record and analyze the data gathered through a self-made survey questionnaire. The consent has been distributed by messaging each one of the target participants of the study. The researchers also informed the participants when the data will be used as a reference for the foregoing study. The participants were also advised that all the data collated was deleted when the study reached its conclusion. Moreover, the names of the participants will not be disclosed as a part of the participant's data privacy. No one in the respondents shall be forced out of their interest to prevent any conflict from it. They are given the choice to partake in the study in the accordance with their interests. Since some of the students are minors, parental consent are given before they partake in the study. This is to prevent any misunderstanding in the data gathering of the study.

In terms of data storing, the researcher has the right and the sole responsibility on storing the gathered data from the study. The researcher is to provide the analysis and treatment for the statistician alone. No one is allowed to handle the data except the researcher themselves.

In terms of conflict of interests, the researcher has detailed some of the conflicts of interest to be not included in the data gathering. The respondents that have conflict over the ideas are not forced to undertake the study.

Results and Discussion

Sub-Problem No. 1 - What are the problems that are encountered in the online and hybrid learning?

Table 2. Problem Encountered in the Online and Hybrid Learning

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Lack of support and encouragement of the administrations to provide training opportunity to the teacher.	2.98	Moderately Encountered
2.	They don't strives to continuously learn and develop their own skills.	2.30	Least Encountered
3.	No master plan for trainings of teachers according to their needs and motivate them towards achieving the school objectives.	2.25	Least Encountered
4.	Inadequate teacher personnel .	2.74	Moderately Encountered
5.	Lack of inadequate training and development for teacher.	2.62	Moderately Encountered
6.	Insufficient time for teaching the concept and specific skills to the learners.	2.54	Least Encountered
7.	Lack of laboratory facilities, equipment, supplies and materials.	2.59	Least Encountered
8.	Overloaded teaching assignment of teachers	2.53	Least Encountered
9.	Lack of funding support for training and development of teachers.	2.58	Least Encountered
10.	Weak school and industry partnership	1.92	Least Encountered
Composite Mean		2.51	Least Encountered

The results shows the problems encountered in the online and hybrid learning. It is determined that the problems are found to be least encountered. It is supported by the composite mean of 2.51 which interprets as least countered. It is claimed in the results that it is moderately encountered the lack of support and encouragement of the administrations to provide training opportunity to the teacher (WM = 2.98). The results also shows that it is least encountered the weak school and industry partnership (WM = 1.92).

Capability includes the capacity to manage a wide range of difficulties in both the calling and in day to day existence. Sieck (2020) showed that the answers for prevailing as an innovator in an association envelop a more extensive assortment of ranges of abilities beside initiative capacities. Hence, various instructors must have specific ways to deal with thinking and acting to do allotted undertakings. Instructors significantly affect the improvement of a local area. The Philippines' drawn out improvement and progression rely upon coordinated understudies who are both established in values and gifted in 21st-century capacities (DepED Request No. 36, s. 2013).

Sub-Problem No. 2 - What is the level of instructional competence of the English teachers in public and private schools in the

COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of:

Classroom Management

The instructional competence of the teachers in terms of classroom management is evaluated. According to the results, a composite mean of 4.03 has been discovered with an interpretation of competent. It is clearly indicated that they are highly competent in imposing discipline to fix incorrect behavior of the students inside the classroom (WM = 4.21). The results also show that the respondents are competent in creating a safe and well maintain learning environment (WM = 3.82).

Table 3. *Level of Instructional Competence of the English Teachers (Classroom Management)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The teachers imposed discipline to fix incorrect behavior of the students inside the classroom	4.21	Highly Competent
2.	The teacher used democratic technique by way of providing equal opportunity for student participation and allows expressing their own ideas and feeling.	3.96	Competent
3.	Proper care of tools, equipment, machine and material to ensure maximum used.	3.87	Competent
4.	Apply safety rules and regulations all the time to prevent accident.	4.05	Competent
5.	Maintain and sustain the physical conditions of the classroom and workshop facilities.	4.19	Competent
6.	Strengthen social relationship with the students.	4.18	Competent
7.	Managing, guiding, and controlling students behavior	3.92	Competent
8.	A safe and well maintain learning environment.	3.82	Competent
Composite Mean		4.03	Competent

As indicated by Gamayao and Biñas (2021), educating and learning are viewed as two pieces of guidance. Educators should have a serious level of skill and educational capacities in the subject they are instructing to be more powerful and effective. The capability of an instructor incorporates the capacities, understanding, and mindset that empower them to satisfy their region doled out commitments.

Teachers/Faculty Qualification and Experience

Table 4. *Level of Instructional Competence of the English Teachers (Teachers/Faculty Qualification and Experience)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The teacher met the qualification standard set forth by the DEpEd/civil service.	4.32	Highly Competent
2.	Knowledge in different area/skills in Mathematics and Expertise in their field of specialization.	4.27	Highly Competent
3.	Knowledge in using (ICT) Information Computer Technology – Integration of Multimedia.	4.02	Competent
4.	Excellent Communication Skills, Verbal and Written.	4.11	Competent
5.	Ability to work harmoniously with their colleagues.	4.04	Competent
6.	Know how to read and interpret syllabus and modules.	4.28	Highly Competent
7.	Avail industry immersion training/ program for teacher.	4.25	Highly Competent
8.	Avails regular upgrading related skills training	4.01	Competent
Composite Mean		4.16	Competent

In terms of teachers or faculty qualification and experience, it can be determined that the respondents are competent. A composite mean of 4.16 has supported this claim with an interpretation of competent. It is found that the teachers are highly competent in meeting the qualification standard set forth by the DEpEd/civil service (WM = 4.32). It is even claimed to be competent on availing regular upgrading related skills training (WM = 4.01).

One of the ramifications of the Coronavirus pandemic lockdown is that schools all over the planet were shut. Konig et al. (2020) uncovered that computerized educator ability and instructor schooling chances to foster advanced skill are significant in acclimating to web based learning. The computerized capability of instructors is exceptionally required since online distance learning is profoundly used. According to Barron et al. (2020), educators' liabilities are changing at a fast speed, making showing now, in many regards, more testing than when only one-on-one instructing was utilized. Instructors currently need to commit a more prominent measure of time to training, speaking with students, and other regulatory obligations. The pandemic highlighted those instructors and understudies need greater adaptability.

Mastery of Subject Taught

Table 5. *Level of Instructional Competence of the English Teachers (Mastery of Subject Taught)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (explain the subject matter without relying solely from the prescribed textbook).	4.05	Competent
2.	Draws and share information of the theory and practice in his/her disciplined	3.94	Competent
3.	Integrates the practical knowledge and experiences to share with the learners.	4.05	Competent
4.	Explains the relevance present topics to the previous lessons, and relates it to the subject matter to the current issues and/ or daily life activities.	4.07	Competent

5. Demonstrates up-to-date knowledge and awareness on current trends and issues of the subject.	4.01	Competent
	Composite Mean 4.02	Competent

As for the Mastery of Subject Taught, the teachers are also found to be competent. It is supported with a composite mean of 4.02 which as analyzed as competent. From the results, it is clearly shown that the teachers are competent at explaining the relevance present topics to the previous lessons, and relates it to the subject matter to the current issues and/ or daily life activities (WM = 4.07). It is even dimmed competent that teachers are drawing and sharing information of the theory and practice in his/her disciplined (WM = 3.94).

Regardless of working from their individual homes, instructors and chiefs have been accused of the undertaking of refreshing and changing course schedules and principles as they progressed to online classes. Learning frameworks like Moodle, Material, and Chalkboard, as well as programming including Google Meet, Zoom, and Video visit, have been utilized in homerooms in which educators and understudies approach online frameworks and respectable Web affiliations. Teachers and managers utilized cell phones to send data, comments, and hardware to schools where individuals had restricted admittance to PCs or erratic Web access (Simbulan, 2020).

Methods, Techniques and Strategies used in Teaching

Table 6. *Level of Instructional Competence of the English Teachers (Methods, Techniques and Strategies used in Teaching)*

Indicator	WM	Interpretation
Develop teaching strategies and techniques that allows learners to expedites learning	4.01	Competent
Enhance learners' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to their outstanding performance/ potentials	4.09	Competent
Allow learners to develop a critical thinking and encourage them with a higher level of competence.	4.01	Competent
Allows learners to think independently and make their own decisions prosper and holding them accountable for their actions.	4.07	Competent
Encourages students to learn beyond what is required that help/guide them how to apply the concepts acquired.	4.05	Competent
Creates opportunities for intensive and/or extensive contribution of students in the class activities	4.06	Competent
Assumes roles as facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, referee in drawing students to contribute the knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hand	4.00	Competent
Designs and implements learning conditions and experience that will promotes healthy exchange and/ or confrontations	4.03	Competent
Structures/re-structures learning and teaching-learning context to enhance the attainment of the collective learning objectives.	4.02	Competent
Uses of Instructional Materials to reinforce learning possess.	4.07	Competent
Used multiple learning strategies with the support system of ICT.	4.05	Competent
	Composite Mean 4.04	Competent

The results show that the teachers are competent in terms of Methods, Techniques and Strategies used in teaching. It is backed by a 4.04 composite mean which indicates competency. As can be observed in the results, it is clear that teachers are competent at enhancing learners' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to their outstanding performance/ potentials (WM = 4.09). It is even indicated that the teachers are competent in assuming roles as facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, referee in drawing students to contribute the knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hand (WM = 4.00).

As society changes to embrace mechanical fates, the way and what educators show in our school system will adjust and should be improved to stay aware of the extending requests of the twenty-first hundred years. The educator's part in utilizing data and correspondence innovation (ICT) in the educating educational experience during the Coronavirus pandemic is basic (Espino-Díaz et al., 2020). Educators should have academic preparation in grasping the utilization of ICT in educating. By doing this, new instructive styles will be made more straightforward to arise to give new information to understudies effectively.

Research and Extension Projects

Table 7. *Level of Instructional Competence of the English Teachers (Research and Extension Projects)*

Indicator	WM	Interpretation
Conducts technical feasibility study and action research to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness in teaching mechanical technology courses.	4.21	Highly Competent
Undertakes feasibility study on the utilization of the indigenous materials to be used in instruction.	3.96	Competent
Established linkages in the local/ national and international levels for finding support and assistance.	3.87	Competent
Create and develop a conducive and well-equipped workplace including a research resource center	4.05	Competent

Generate income from patents, licenses, copyrights and other research output.	4.19	Competent
Conduct research outputs that are utilized as inputs to institutional development.	4.18	Competent
Supports the educational fund raising program of the community.	3.92	Competent
Joins the Alay – Lakad activity in the barangay/community	3.82	Competent
Helps the community in promoting the clean and green and recycling program	4.19	Competent
Design short term technical training program to educate the out of school youth eradicate the unemployment problems in the community	3.93	Competent
Conduct community immersion program thru mobile/technology on wheel for technology transfer.	3.84	Competent
Encourages instructors and students to promote community projects/programs.	4.04	Competent
Support the risk reduction management program in the community.	4.17	Competent
Composite Mean	4.03	Competent

The results of the data gathering also shown the level of instructional competence in terms of research and extension projects. From the results, a composite mean of 4.03 has been discovered with an interpretation of competent. An indication of the results show that they are highly competent in conducting technical feasibility study and action research to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness in teaching mechanical technology courses (WM = 4.21). Another indication shows that teachers are competent in joining the Alay – Lakad activity in the barangay/community (WM = 3.82).

It is essential for a teacher to begin maximizing productivity because it is a career path that is extremely close to students and a field of study that is always available to assist students in maximizing their skills (Intan & Ahmad, 2016). The nature of understudies is a consequence of great training. When it comes to providing education of a high quality, teachers become crucial success factors.

Sub-Problem No. 3 - What is the performance of the teachers as assessed in the IPCRF rating?

Table 8. Performance of the Teachers

Performance of Teachers (IPCRF Rating)	4.15	Very Satisfactory
--	------	-------------------

The IPCRF Rating of the teachers show that the teachers are very satisfactory in their performance. The mean of 4.15 has been discovered. This shows that teachers are performing well at a very satisfactory rating.

Lepp et al. (2021) suggested that choices educators make in showing influence their understudies' learning execution. Instructors' instructing related activities are influenced by components, for example, advanced innovations' presence and capacity to be utilized. To keep up with class association and to help understudies' inspiration, educators pursued the greater part of their showing choices in light of points that were more transitory in nature, for example, advancing social contact.

Sub-Problem No. 4 - Is there a significant difference between the instructional competence of the teachers and the performance of the teachers as assessed by both students and colleague?

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing

Variable	p-value	Sig	Decision
Instructional Competence vs. Performance of the Teachers	0.004253	Significant	Reject Ho

The results of the hypothesis testing show that the instructional competence and the performance of the teachers are significant. A p-value of 0.004253 has been discovered and indicates significance. This implies uniqueness of the instructional competence and the performance of the teachers.

The concentrate by Iqbal et al. (2019) found that understudies' assessment of their speakers' ability impacts the learning fulfillment and experience of students. In this way, magnificent talks ensure more prominent learning results for understudies. A positive connection is linked to student-teacher interaction. Instructors who are given the opportunity and backing to put themselves out there inventively altogether affect understudies' advancing as well as the advancement of their personality characteristics.

Conclusions

The research findings indicate several key outcomes regarding online and hybrid learning experiences. It is determined that the challenges faced in these learning environments are minimal. However, there is a moderate experience of insufficient support from institutions in providing training opportunities for educators. The educational competence of teachers in classroom management is assessed, showing that they are highly proficient in maintaining discipline to correct student misbehavior. It is inferred that the respondents are qualified and experienced educators, meeting the standards set by the Department of Education (DepEd) and civil service requirements. Regarding subject mastery, teachers are found to be competent. They effectively connect current topics with previous lessons and relate them to real-life situations and contemporary issues. The results highlight that educators are proficient in employing various teaching methods and techniques. They are adept at enhancing student self-esteem and recognizing their exceptional performance and potential. The data also demonstrate the high level of educational competence in research and extension projects,

particularly in conducting technical feasibility studies and action research to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching technological courses.

The teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings indicate very satisfactory performance, showcasing their high competence. The hypothesis testing results reveal a significant correlation between instructional competence and teacher performance, suggesting the uniqueness and importance of these competencies.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. It is suggested that teachers frequently attend training and seminar programs to enhance their preparedness for school management roles and to continuously improve their teaching skills and performance. School heads and principals are advised to improve their evaluation and monitoring systems, including the IPCRF of teachers. Programs for educators should focus on assessing their teaching abilities, especially during the pandemic, and provide strategies for balancing work and career. Further research should be conducted to explore various aspects of school administrators' leadership skills and their application in different areas of school performance and operations.

References

- Abuhammad, S. (2020). Barriers to distance learning during the COVID-19 outbreak: A qualitative review from parents' perspective. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844020323252>
- Barron, M. et al. (2021). The changing role of teachers and technologies amidst the COVID 19 pandemic: key findings from a cross-country study. Retrieved from: <https://blogs.worldbank.org/education/changing-role-teachers-and-technologies-amidst-covid-19-pandemic-key-findings-cross>
- Baticulon, R. et al. (2021). Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40670-021-01231-z#Abs1>
- Chriscaden, K. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on people's livelihoods, their health and our food systems. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/13-10-2020-impact-of-covid-19-on-people-s-livelihoods-their-health-and-our-food-systems>
- CoSN (2020). COVID-19 Response: Preparing to Take School Online. Retrieved from: https://www.cosn.org/sites/default/files/COVID-19%20Member%20Exclusive_0.pdf
- European Training Foundation (2020). Teachers play an important role in boosting learners' engagement in education affected by the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Espino- Diaz, L. et al. (2020). Analyzing the Impact of COVID-19 on Education Professionals. Toward a Paradigm Shift: ICT and Neuroeducation as a Binomial of Action. Retrieved from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/14/5646>
- Gamayao, M. & Biñas, E. (2021). Eaching Competence And Pedagogical Content Knowledge Of Science Teachersin The First District Of Capiz, Philippines: Basis For A Sustainableinstructional Program. Retrieved from: <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejhea/article/view/147/123>
- Gotinga, J. (2020). To boost students' competence, PH needs better teacher training – Gatchalian. Retrieved from: <https://www.rappler.com/nation/gatchalian-says-philippines-needs-better-teacher-training>
- Hasegawa, K. (2012). Instructional Competencies Of The Teaching Force: Their Relationship To The Students' Academic Performance. Retrieved from: https://www.academia.edu/10728894/INSTRUCTIONAL_COMPETENCIES_OF_THE_TEACHING_FORCE_THEIR_RELATIONSHIP_TO_THE_STUDENTS_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE?email_work_card=view-paper
- Hartini, S. et al. (2018). Teacher Pedagogic Competency Development Model: A Literature Review. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329956814_Teacher_Pedagogic_Competency_Development_Model_A_Literature_Review
- Intan & Ahmad (2016). Arah & Kebijakan Kementerian Riset, Teknologi, dan Pendidikan Tinggi: Kurikulum dan Sistem Pembelajaran LPTK. Retrieved from: <http://seminars.unj.ac.id/konaspi/>
- Iqbal, A. et al. (2019). Effect of Teachers' Competencies on Scholars' Academic Achievement and Satisfaction. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342764076_Effect_of_Teachers'_Competencies_on_Scholars'_Academic_Achievement_and_Satisfaction
- Kim, S. et al. (2019). Improving 21st-century teaching skills: The key to effective 21st-century learners. Retrieved from: https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1745499919829214?fbclid=IwAR0tqaC_v6VojtjfyAD-9VzP8SWFazuRgrw-42a9fKRv63dYP2d_gDwUzzDk#
- Konig, J. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02619768.2020.1809650>

- Lapitan, L. et al. (2021). An effective blended online teaching and learning strategy during the COVID-19 pandemic. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1749772821000129>
- Lepp, L. et al. (2021). Teaching during COVID-19: The Decisions Made in Teaching. Retrieved from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/11/2/47>
- Mahyoob, M. (2020). Challenges of e-Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic Experienced by EFL Learners. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1287713.pdf>
- Mazariegos, L.G.R. (2020). The Professionalization of Teachers: Competencies for the 21-st Century. Retrieved from: <https://observatory.tec.mx/edu-bits-2/competencies-for-the-21st-century-teacher>
- Murgatrottd, S. (2020). COVID-19 and Online learning, Alberta, Canada. doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.31132.8512
- Muthuprasad, T. et al. (2021). Students' perception and preference for online education in India during COVID -19 pandemic. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590291120300905#bib7>
- Prasertcharoensuk, T. et al. (2015). Influence of Teacher Competency Factors and Students' Life Skills on Learning Achievement. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277964535_Influence_of_Teacher_Competency_Factors_and_Students'_Life_Skills_on_Learning_Achievement
- Rojas II, J.F. (2021). Flexible learning as the new normal. Retrieved from: <https://businessmirror.com.ph/2021/05/24/flexible-learning-as-the-new-normal/>
- Sieck, W. (2020). What is Competence and Why is it Important?. Retrieved from: <https://www.globalcognition.org/what-is-competence/>
- Simbulan, N. (2020). The Philippines – COVID-19 and Its Impact on Higher Education in the Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://headfoundation.org/2020/06/04/covid-19-and-its-impact-on-higher-education-in-the-philippines/>
- Sootipon, J. (2010). The changes of learning world in the 21st Century and development for professional teachers. Retrieved from: http://hu.swu.ac.th/hu/km/Files/2_Changes_in_the-world.21pdf.
- Tongson, M. & Eslit, E. (2018). Teaching Styles And Language Performance: Towards A Development Of An English Language Program. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED590796.pdf>
- Tria, J. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdll/8311>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Robert Niño O. Ponce, LPT, CRS

San Jose Community High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Rochelle P. Cañares, LPT

General Mariano Alvarez Technical High School
Department of Education – Philippines